

Buddies

by Brian Paul Kaess

Right 'off the bat,' let me add as a disclaimer, that it be known that I served in three branches: the **U.S. Army, Illinois Army National Guard, and U.S. Marines**. In the Army and Guard, I went by Sp/4 Brian Paul Kaess and in the Marines I was LCpl. Brian 'Chaos' Kaess (Ret.). Nowadays, I am a U.S. Disabled Veteran living in Durango, Mexico. Basically, 'Jo-blo Civilian!'

When I was in **U.S. Army** Basic Training, I remember Drill Instructor Robertson as saying, 'Men, your pain will be your gain, your pain will be your gain.' Also, I remember Sp4 Tim Walker and Sp4 Mills, both African Americans who had served in the U.S. Army in Europe, urging me to look for my Family in Europe. I vowed after I left the Army, I would look for them. In 1990, I did, in fact, reunite with family in Germany.

So, my buddies/fellow soldiers in the **U.S. Army** included Wojikowski (from WI), Lockery, Walker (from VA Beach), Mills, Niles Arrington (Ranger Vet, from Markham, IL, wife was German gal Karen), Sgt. Jones (from RI, NG SF), Pvt. Sayre (Reserve SF), Sally (a black soldier in AIT with green eyes), Black (southerner who was into Confederate Heritage and reenactment groups while on active duty), the Odoms (a married IR soldier duo), Riddick, Lt Bey (Bey & Riddick were married and were both from Chicago), Moton (married from Chicago), Vern (skinniest dude I knew in the Army), Helgenson (tattoo man), John (SSG, a black Vietnam Vet who served in 25th ID), Mitchell (married, a Language School drop), Cpl Roy (married from Philly), Tracey (knew me and roommate Garret), red-haired Tracey (?)(SSG, my AIT Instructor, husband was SF, friend to Ellen and I at Ft. Sam), SFC Fischer (Airborne), SSG Wooden (husband was SF), Drill SSG Robertson (AA, EIB), Drill SSG Swift (Airborne, Grenada Vet), SSG Paul Jones (LPN, from WV, wife was Wanda), SSG Paul Skurka (best Ranger '86), & LtCol Leonard B. Scott (Airborne Commandant, patted him on the back during a PT run), roommates Dejarmin (Swedish-American, married) & Hernandez (volunteered for SF) & Garrett (from Barbados) & Johnson (Michigan State grad). Sgt. Irizarry (LPN, from NY/Puerto Rico), Sp/4 Rodriguez (Puerto Rico). Then there was this blond chick I nicknamed 'the fish head,' her husband was Airborne/Air Assault. She made a pass at me at Ft. A.P. Hill wearing a towel. Leo (RIP buddy, Italian-American). Dude (from RIP) from Chicago I nicknamed Kelly cause he was from Kelly H.S.- he liked prostitutes and wanted me to stay. Shoto-Kon dude from Medic AIT- knew cool martial arts. An attractive, black female GI (her husband was a Captain) in the 438th who urged me to go to AA school at Davis, but I opted for EFMB at Fort Meade instead. This same GI bought a car from my wife Ellen. There was also a Jewish male soldier in our outfit, who loved raving about the IDF and how strong it was. I found it amusing. He sold us his used car (a chic design) and then we resold it to a black female soldier (just mentioned) in the very same unit (438th). There was also the former Royal Marine Commando who transitioned as a Ranger Instructor SSG. A Vietnam Vet, he was so renowned in martial arts that it was thought that he was rated 2nd in the world in Judo. Once, he joked, that in Vietnam during a tour with the U.S. Army, when Charlie was attacking, he had to pull up his skivies during a latrine run, and shout, 'Charlies' coming! Charlies' coming!'

Because of the short duration of my 'stint' in the **Illinois Army National Guard**, I didn't know too many names. There was a Polish chick named Lisa, who served in the same unit (508th Medical Company), but I only knew her threw my civilian job later.

In the **Marines**, I liked Drill Instructor Sgt. Oxner because he would say, 'They ain't got what we got!' reinforcing Esprit de Corps. Another would say, 'Pop smoke! We're moving!' and Sgt. Romero would say, 'Road guards! Be strong!' It was Sgt. Romero who lectured to us about GySgt. John Basilone's Medal of Honor citation. I felt like I knew that guy!

My buddies or other **U.S. Marines** I worked with included Galaz, Lamb, Westover, Antoine LaCount, Chad Beller, Van Hoosen, Nichols, Johnson, Sherman, Fire, Riley, Snow, Theobald, Salamanca-Medina, Delgado, Fleming (from TX), Knox, (from TX) Facets, Phelps, Fitzgerald, Foreman (from Chi-town), Harris, Bennett, Zimmerman, Plough, Davenport, Becker, Gower, Barret, Banderas, Monge, Meisner (Christian southerner from AK), Scroggins, Sgt Gonzalez, Sgt Lidl, Sgt. Romero, Sgt Collins, Sgt George, SSG Cross, SSG Paige, SSG Tejas (from TX), GySgt Jury, Maj Aiken, Col Bamford, Cpl Cook, Lt Ring, & Capt Petrucci.

There were **U.S. Navy** folks to include: Enke (from TX), Liz (from TX), Heather (from PA), Gigi (Hispanic), and Dr. Chronin (O-6 Captain & Surgeon). These were people I bumped into on 'Gitmo' and managed to catch their names.

Besides these wonderful service folks, I also want to thank as 'buddies' my two **wives**, Capt. Ellen Byrd Elliott (from Ohio), USAR, LPN, RN, and Mayte Urbina Pereda (from Mexico) as well as any supportive 'family, friends and pets that gets you to the finish line!' And, of course, my all-time favorite buddy was my twin-brother 2nd Lt. Garret Thomas Kaess, as well as my son Paul Jesus Kaess. Then there were my aunts Ursula & Arnhild Kaess. Obviously, my dog Tommy and cats Nieve & Candy & Sabrina were very special and never failed to lend a paw!

Gratefully,

Brian P. Kaess